

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN PSYCHOLOGICAL STRESS AND MANAGERIAL QUALITIES IN DEPARTMENT HEADS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Mamatkulova Kimyoxon Abdujalilovna
Tashkent named after Nizami
state pedagogical university
Associate Professor, Doctor of
Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Annotation

This article examines the correlation between psychological stress and managerial qualities in department heads of higher education institutions. The study shows that increased stress can hinder effective leadership, while emotional stability and resilience support the development of strong managerial competencies.

Keywords: psychological stress, managerial qualities, department head, higher education, leadership competence, emotional stability, academic management.

It is important to note that one of the main objectives of our research is to study the influence of psychological stress on the manifestation of managerial qualities in department heads working in higher education institutions. Specifically, the research aims to determine how the level of psychological stress experienced by department heads affects the development of their managerial competencies.

For this purpose, two methodologies were applied to the respondent groups: R.S. Nemov's "Leader" method and N.E. Vodopyanova's "Psychological Stress Scale." These tools allow for the identification of how psychological stress indicators—such as emotional instability, sudden mood decline, and dissatisfaction with one's profession or self—impact the manifestation of managerial qualities.

The methods were administered to a group of department heads, and the data collected were analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table-1

**The Relationship Between Managerial Competence and Psychological Stress in
Department Heads of Higher Education Institutions (N=320)**

(Based on Pearson Correlation Criterion)

Component	Respondents	Psychological Stress (r)
Managerial Qualities	Male Department Heads	-0.51**
	Female Department Heads	-0.44**

Note: * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$

According to the results of the methodology (see Table 1), a significant negative correlation was identified between managerial qualities and psychological stress among male department heads in higher education institutions ($r = -0.51$; $p \leq 0.01$). This indicates that the level of emotional strain directly affects the manifestation of managerial traits in respondents. High stress levels often lead to difficulties in managing emotions during challenging work situations, a lack of behavioral self-reflection, reduced motivation to solve problems, and a tendency toward hopelessness. Moreover, such negative conditions in the professional environment can hinder the development of managerial qualities. As a result, department heads may experience difficulties concentrating when making critical decisions and may suffer from a decline in positive thinking and problem-solving skills.

At the same time, when examining the results of female department heads in higher education institutions, it was found that managerial qualities also exhibit a negative correlation with psychological stress ($r = -0.44$; $p \leq 0.01$). These findings suggest that feelings of emotional exhaustion and dissatisfaction with one's internal experiences can contribute to a reduced ability to manage both oneself and others in a professional context. Furthermore, increased psychological stress may lead to losing composure in challenging situations, giving in to negative emotions, abandoning professional goals, and losing confidence in the future success of departmental activities—behaviors that are inconsistent with strong managerial competence.

In conclusion, when analyzing the effect of psychological stress on the manifestation of managerial qualities in department heads, a clear negative relationship between the two variables emerges. In particular, frequent emotional strain, ongoing fatigue, and difficulty in managing emotions may result in distraction from leadership responsibilities and difficulties in making sound decisions. These indicators confirm that the level of psychological stress directly affects the emergence and development of managerial competencies in department heads.

References

1. Водопьянова, Н.Е. Психодиагностика стресса. – Санкт-Петербург: Речь, 2009. – 288 с.
2. Немов, Р.С. Психология: Учебник для студентов педвузов. – М.: Владос, 2003. – Т. 3. – 688 с.
3. Ахмедова, Д.М. Бошқарув фаолиятида шахснинг стрессга мойиллиги ва унинг психологик жиҳатлари. // Психология: илмий-амалий журнал. – 2022. – №4(78). – Б. 115–120.